

FREQUENCY OF POSITIVE CHEST X-RAY FINDINGS IN CHILDREN AGED 2-59 MONTHS CLASSIFIED AS PNEUMONIA ACCORDING TO IMNCI GUIDELINES

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Abstract

Background: Pneumonia significantly impacts children under five, with chest X-ray being used for long time for confirmation despite of its limitations. Integrated Management of Neonatal and Childhood Illness offers a clinical alternative, yet literature shows variable agreement, prompting this study to evaluate positive X-ray findings in IMNCI-classified pneumonia.

Objectives: To determine the frequency of positive x-ray findings in children with age 2-59 months classified as pneumonia according to IMNCI guidelines.

Duration: Six months i.e. from 03-08-2024 to 02-02-2025.

Methodology: One hundred and eighty children aged 2-59 months having cough and / or difficulty breathing of less than four weeks duration, breathing fast, or chest indrawing were included and classified as pneumonia using IMNCI guidelines. All children underwent chest X-rays, interpreted by a senior consultant. Findings were analyzed using SPSS version 27.0.

Results: A total of 180 children aged 2-59 months, diagnosed with pneumonia as per IMNCI guidelines, were included. The mean age was 30.82±16.27 months. Boys were 57.2% (n=103) and girls were 42.8% (n=77). Chest X-ray was positive in 150 (83.3%) cases, without significant subgroup differences.

Conclusion: This study concluded that the majority of children aged 2-59 months diagnosed with pneumonia according to IMNCI guidelines showed positive chest X-ray findings. No significant differences were observed across age, gender, or symptom duration, indicating that radiological evidence strongly supports IMNCI-based clinical diagnosis in pediatric pneumonia cases.

INTRODUCTION

Pneumonia is a lung or pulmonary parenchymal infection, and remains a major cause of childhood morbidity and mortality worldwide. Globally, the annual incidence is more than 1,400 cases per 100,000 children, translating to approximately one case per 71 children.¹ It is also one of the leading infectious causes of mortality, contributing to 14% of all deaths in children under five years of age.^{1,2} The majority of these deaths occur in low- and

middle-income countries where healthcare facilities are limited, and many of the improvements done in health care system in developed regions are not widely available in developing countries.³

In 2015, global estimates revealed that Pakistan, along with four other countries, accounted for 52% of pneumonia episodes and nearly half (49%) of pneumonia-related deaths. Each year, approximately 58,000 children under five years die of pneumonia

in Pakistan.⁴ Clinical signs of pneumonia typically include fever, tachypnea and auscultatory crackles in 80% of cases, while up to 30% may demonstrate consolidation. Despite these features, accurate diagnosis of pneumonia in children remains challenging.^{4,5} The IMNCI guidelines, based on clinical parameters, have been adopted by WHO and UNICEF and have contributed to a 30–40% reduction in pneumonia-related mortality when followed appropriately.^{5,6}

The IMNCI framework defines severe pneumonia as cough or difficult breathing of less than three weeks' duration, accompanied by tachypnea for the respective age group (≥ 50 breaths/min for ages 2–12 months and ≥ 40 breaths/min for 12–59 months) and lower chest wall indrawing.⁷ Although chest radiography (CXR) has long been considered the gold standard for pneumonia diagnosis, its role remains debated.⁸ While chest X-rays are often used to assess severity, some studies report strong correlations between radiographic findings and clinical pneumonia, whereas others do not.⁶ For instance, Amjad et al. reported a frequency of positive CXR findings as high as 86.5% in children aged 2–59 months who were clinically classified with pneumonia using IMNCI criteria at Mayo Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan.⁹ This suggests that reliance on IMNCI guidelines could reduce unnecessary exposure to X-rays, minimize costs, and prove particularly useful in rural areas with limited diagnostic resources.

However, evidence from other studies shows considerable variability. Chethan et al. in India reported 64.8% positive chest X-ray findings in IMNCI-classified pneumonia cases,¹⁰ Jiskani et al. in Pakistan reported 38%,⁸ and Elfving et al. documented as low as 10%.¹¹ This inconsistency in findings, even across similar populations, highlights the need for further evaluation. Therefore, the present study was conducted to compare and validate the frequency of positive X-ray findings in IMNCI-diagnosed pneumonia cases. The findings of this study provide evidence that may support broader implementation of IMNCI guidelines to reduce unnecessary radiographic exposure and healthcare costs.

METHODOLOGY

This research was a descriptive cross-sectional study carried out in the Department of Paediatric Medicine at Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore. It was conducted over a period of six months following the approval of the synopsis. A total of 180 cases were included, with the sample size determined at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, based on an anticipated frequency of positive chest X-ray findings of 86.5% in children aged 2–59 months diagnosed with pneumonia according to IMNCI guidelines.⁹ The sampling method adopted was non-probability consecutive sampling.

Pneumonia was defined according to IMNCI guidelines. Severe pneumonia was considered present in children with cough or difficulty in breathing for less than three weeks, along with increased respiratory rate according to age (for children aged 2–12 months, >50 breaths per minute, and for children aged 12–59 months, >40 breaths per minute), as well as the presence of lower chest indrawing. Positive chest X-ray findings were defined as the presence of at least two of the following features on a posteroanterior (PA) chest X-ray, as reported by a radiologist: (i) lung consolidation, observed as a white area in the lung; (ii) lung collapse, defined as collapse of an entire lobe of the lung with a denser appearance due to air filling the pleural space between the lung and chest wall; and (iii) reticular shadowing, appearing as a pattern of fine linear opacities resembling a net or mesh.

The inclusion criteria were children of either gender aged between 2 and 59 months who were diagnosed as pneumonia according to IMNCI guidelines, as defined above. Exclusion criteria included children with bronchial asthma, bronchiolitis, congenital heart disease, pleural effusion due to other causes, or severe anemia presenting with congestive or acquire cardiac failure. These exclusions were applied to minimize confounding variables and ensure a homogenous study population.

A total of 180 patients presenting to the outpatient ward and / or emergency sections of the Department of Paediatrics, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore, with symptoms of cough and/or difficulty in breathing of less than four weeks' duration were enrolled. On examination, children having fast

breathing (respiratory rate >50 per minute for ages 2–11 months, and >40 per minute for ages 12–59 months) or lower chest wall indrawing were classified as pneumonia according to IMNCI guidelines. All patients underwent routine chest X-rays as per the hospital’s standard protocol, and no patient was deprived of radiographic assessment, irrespective of IMNCI classification. Every patient was provided treatment according to individual clinical findings. Children diagnosed with pneumonia based on IMNCI guidelines were further assessed radiologically, and positive X-ray findings were recorded. Classification of pneumonia according to IMNCI and X-ray findings was performed by the same senior consultant, while all X-rays were conducted in the same laboratory of the hospital to reduce bias. Confounding variables were controlled by applying the exclusion criteria.

The collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 27.0. Continuous variables, including age and duration of symptoms, were expressed as mean ±SD, while categorical variables, such as gender and the proportion of positive chest X-ray findings, were shown as frequency and percentage. To address potential effect modifiers, data were stratified by age, gender, and duration of symptoms. Following stratification, the chi-square test was employed, and a p-value ≤0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 180 children aged 2–59 months, classified as pneumonia according to IMNCI guidelines, were included in the study. The mean age of the children was 30.82±16.27 months. Among them, 88 (48.9%) were between 2–30 months of age, while 92 (51.1%) were between 31–59 months. With respect to gender distribution, boys constituted the majority, accounting for 103 cases (57.2%), whereas girls were 77 (42.8%). The mean duration of symptoms was 1.47±0.50 weeks. Most of the children, 96 (53.3%), had symptoms for one week, whereas 84 (46.7%) had symptoms for two weeks. Data is given in Table 1.

Table 2 shows that out of 180 children diagnosed with pneumonia as per IMNCI guidelines, 150 (83.3%) had positive chest X-ray findings while 30 (16.7%) had no radiographic evidence of pneumonia. Table 3 shows that among children aged 2–30 months, 71 (80.7%) had positive chest X-ray findings compared to 79 (85.9%) in those aged 31–59 months (p=0.351). With respect to gender, 87 boys (84.5%) and 63 girls (81.8%) demonstrated positive findings (p=0.637). Considering duration of symptoms, 81 children (84.4%) with one-week history and 69 children (82.1%) with two-week history showed radiographic evidence of pneumonia (p=0.688). None of the subgroup comparisons reached statistical significance.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Children with Pneumonia as per IMNCI Guidelines

Characteristics	Total (180)
Age (2-59 months)	30.82±16.27
• 2-30 months	88 (48.9%)
• 31-59 months	92 (51.1%)
Gender	
• Boy	103 (57.2%)
• Girl	77 (42.8%)
Duration of Symptoms	1.47±0.50
• 1-week	96 (53.3%)
• 2-week	84 (46.7%)

Table 2: Frequency of Pneumonia as per Positive X-ray Findings in Children Diagnosed with Pneumonia as per IMNCI Guidelines

Pneumonia	Positive X-ray Findings
• Yes	150 (83.3%)
• No	30 (16.7%)

Table 3: Frequency of Pneumonia as per Positive X-ray Findings in Children Diagnosed with Pneumonia as per IMNCI Guidelines Stratified for Subgroups

Groups / Sub Groups	N	Positive X-ray Findings		p-value
		Yes	No	
Age (2-59 months)				
• 2-30 months	88	71 (80.7%)	17 (19.3%)	0.351
• 31-59 months	92	79 (85.9%)	13 (14.1%)	
Gender				
• Boy	103	87 (84.5%)	16 (15.5%)	0.637
• Girl	77	63 (81.8%)	14 (18.2%)	
Duration of Symptoms				
• 1-week	96	81 (84.4%)	15 (15.6%)	0.688
• 2-week	84	69 (82.1%)	15 (17.9%)	

Chi-Square test, taking p-value ≤ 0.05 as significant.

DISCUSSION

Pneumonia is a major cause of illness and death in children under five worldwide.¹⁰ Chest X-ray has long been used to confirm pneumonia, but its limited availability, cost, and interpretation issues restrict its routine use.¹² To overcome these barriers, the IMNCI guidelines were developed, enabling diagnosis through simple clinical signs such as cough, rapid breathing, and chest indrawing.^{13,14} Despite its widespread use, debate continues in existing literature regarding the accuracy of IMNCI compared with radiographic confirmation, with studies showing variable results.^{8,11} This uncertainty highlighted the need for the present study to assess the frequency of positive chest X-ray findings.

Comparison of the findings of the present study with previously published literature highlights both similarities and variations in the frequency of positive chest X-ray findings among children diagnosed with pneumonia according to IMNCI guidelines. In this study, chest radiography confirmed pneumonia in 83.3% of children aged 2–59 months. These findings are in close agreement with the results of Amjad et al., who conducted their research at Mayo Hospital, Lahore, and reported a

frequency of 86.5% in children diagnosed as pneumonia using IMNCI criteria.⁹ The similarity between the two studies strengthens the validity of IMNCI classification as a reliable clinical tool for diagnosing pneumonia in resource-limited settings.

In contrast, other studies have shown lower frequencies. For instance, Chethan et al. from India reported positive chest X-ray findings in 64.8% of children classified as pneumonia under IMNCI guidelines, indicating a moderate level of correlation between clinical assessment and radiographic evidence.¹⁰ Even lower results were reported by Jiskani et al. in Pakistan, who observed only 38.0% of cases showing radiographic confirmation, suggesting variability in diagnostic accuracy across different populations and healthcare settings.⁶ The lowest frequency was documented by Elfving et al., who reported positive findings in just 10.0% of clinically diagnosed pneumonia cases.¹¹

Uwemedimo et al. in Malawi found poor care quality, with low IMNCI adherence and missed diagnoses in most pneumonia cases.¹⁶ Haque et al. in Pakistan reported IMNCI as a reliable screening tool, demonstrating good sensitivity, specificity, and positive predictive value (PPV), supporting timely

recognition and early intervention in children under five.¹⁷ Ginsburg et al. highlighted that among children with IMNCI chest-indrawing pneumonia, lung ultrasound offered higher interrater reliability than chest X-ray when interpreted by experts. They concluded that lung ultrasound could serve as a preferred diagnostic standard, though its success in low-resource settings depends on adequate clinical adaptation and user training.¹⁸

These variations in results may be attributed to differences in study design, patient population, severity of illness at presentation, radiographic interpretation criteria, and healthcare infrastructure. They also reflect the ongoing debate in existing literature about the sensitivity and specificity of IMNCI guidelines when compared with radiographic confirmation. Despite this variability, the current study, along with Amjad et al., supports that IMNCI criteria demonstrate strong concordance with chest X-ray findings. This suggests that IMNCI remains a useful, practical, and cost-effective diagnostic approach, especially in settings where radiographic facilities are limited.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that the majority of children aged 2–59 months diagnosed with pneumonia according to IMNCI guidelines showed positive chest X-ray findings. No significant differences were observed across age, gender, or symptom duration, indicating that radiographic evidence strongly supports IMNCI-based clinical diagnosis in pediatric pneumonia cases.

LIMITATIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The strength of this study lies in its adequate sample size, standardized diagnostic criteria, and consistent interpretation by a single consultant, minimizing bias. However, being a single-center study limits generalizability, and radiographic interpretation remains subjective. Future studies should be multi-centered, incorporate advanced imaging modalities like lung ultrasound, and assess long-term clinical outcomes.

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Authors Contribution

Author 1

Substantial contributions to study design, synopsis write up, acquisition of data

Analysis & Interpretation of Data, Manuscript writing

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

Author 2 & 3

Substantial contributions to concept, study design.

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Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

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